

SYNTHESIS AND REACTIONS OF SOME HYDROXYMETHYLENE KETONES

BY R. R. AGARWAL, S. M. GUPTA AND S. S. DESHAPANDE

Hydroxymethylene di-*n*-propyl ketone and hydroxymethylene di-*isobutyl* ketone have been synthesised and characterised. Reduction of hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone by sodium amalgam gave 2-methylene-cyclohexanone; while by the action of phosphorus pentachloride, 1:1-dichlorocyclohexane-2-aldehyde was obtained.

Aliphatic symmetrical ketones, higher than diethyl ketone, are comparatively less common. Two of such ketones, viz., di-*n*-propyl ketone and di-*isobutyl* ketone (I, R = Et and R = *isopropyl* respectively), were available in small amounts in these laboratories. The 2-formyl derivatives (II) of these ketones are not described in literature, and in connection with the work of estimating enol content of 2-formyl ketones (Bokadia and Deshapande, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 455) which have mostly the hydroxymethylene structure (III), we have now prepared and characterised them.

(I)

(II)

(III)

The hydroxymethylene ketones were prepared by the usual method as given in the experimental part. Hydroxymethylene di-*n*-propyl ketone (C₉H₁₄O₂) forms a green chelate copper compound (C₁₆H₂₆O₄Cu, m.p. 122°) and a semicarbazone (m.p. 154°) but hydroxymethylene di-*isobutyl* ketone (C₁₀H₁₈O₂) does not yield a chelate copper compound or a semicarbazone.

The two functional groups of hydroxymethylene ketones are keto and aldehyde (II), or in the enolic form, keto and hydroxymethylene (III). It is possible that either the former or the latter group or both of them may simultaneously react with a reagent. For instance, with phosphorus pentachloride, a hydroxymethylene ketone may give 1:1-dichloro-2-aldehyde (IV) or the chloromethylene ketone (V) or 1:1-dichloro-2-chloromethylene compound (VI).

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

Again, addition of hydrogen may take place at the hydroxymethylene group producing the keto-carbinol (hydroxymethyl ketone) (VII) or at both the functional groups producing the glycol (VIII).

(VII)

(VIII)

With sodium and alcohol, hydroxymethylene camphor (IX) is reduced to camphylglycol (X) (Bredt, *Annalen*, 1909, 366, 22). Under similar conditions hydroxymethylene menthone is reduced to menthylglycol (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1901, II, 796). Hydrogen in presence of specially

prepared nickel catalyst gives, however, camphylcarbinol (hydroxymethyl camphor) (XI) (Rupe, Ackermann and Takagi, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1918, 1, 452).

In this reaction methylene camphor (XII) is obtained as a byproduct.

Catalytic reduction of hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone (XIII) in presence of colloidal palladium yields 2-methylcyclohexanone (Kötze and Schaeffer, *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 1954).

Hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone was reduced with sodium amalgam or aluminium amalgam at the temperature of ice, keeping the medium slightly acid. After removing the unchanged hydroxymethylene ketone by dissolving it in alkali, a thick viscous neutral liquid was obtained which gave no colour with ferric chloride. It could not be purified, but from the crude product a semicarbazone was prepared (m.p. 228°). On distillation under reduced pressure, a thin liquid (b.p. 133°-135°/55 mm.) was obtained in almost quantitative yield. The pure liquid on analysis gave results corresponding with the composition $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{10}\text{O}$. The result of analysis of its semicarbazone (m.p. 162°) corresponds with the composition of the semicarbazone of the ketone $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{10}\text{O}$. A solution of this ketone in chloroform readily absorbed bromine proving it to be an unsaturated ketone. The ketone is therefore 2-methylenecyclohexanone (XV) formed probably by loss of a molecule of water during distillation of hydroxymethylcyclohexanone (XIV) contained in the thick viscous liquid.

That the ketone is not 2-methylcyclohexanone is further proved by the difference in the melting points of the semicarbazones of the two ketones (2-methylcyclohexanone semicarbazone, m.p. 193°).

The action of phosphorus pentachloride on hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone in benzene solution at the temperature of ice took place at the keto group instead of at the hydroxymethylene group. The product obtained in good yield proved to be a neutral dichloro aldehyde $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{10}\text{OCl}_2$, with strong reducing properties. It does not dissolve in alkali and does not give colour with ferric chloride. It is therefore 1:1-dichlorocyclohexane-2 aldehyde (XVI). It forms a semicarbazone which melts at 232° and has composition $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{OClN}_3$. The semicarbazide removed one molecule of hydrochloric acid in the process of semicarbazone formation.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Hydroxymethylene-di-n-propyl Ketone.—A mixture of di-*n*-propyl ketone (15g., b.p. 142°) and ethyl formate (12 g.) was gradually added to a suspension of alcohol-free sodium ethylate (11.1 g.) in dry ether at 0°. The contents were shaken and kept at 0° for 4 hours and then at room temperature for 2 days. The sodium compound of the hydroxymethylene ketone formed was filtered at the pump, washed with ether and decomposed with dilute sulphuric acid. The crude hydroxymethylene ketone was extracted with ether and after drying, the solvent was removed. The residual liquid distilled at 115°/80 mm., yield 6.2 g. (Found: C, 66.6; H, 9.9. $C_9H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 67.7; H, 9.8 per cent).

The hydroxymethylene ketone is a pale yellow, mobile liquid which gives violet colour with ferric chloride: On adding cold concentrated copper acetate solution to its alcoholic solution, the copper compound of the ketone separated as a light green crystalline mass. It separated from chloroform-petroleum ether mixture in light green small crystals, m.p. 122°. (Found: Cu, 18.7. $C_{16}H_{26}O_4Cu$ requires Cu, 18.4 per cent).

The ketone forms a semicarbazone which after crystallisation from aqueous alcohol melts at 154°.

Hydroxymethylene-di-isobutyl ketone was prepared from di-isobutyl ketone (b.p. 165°) in the same manner as in the case of the lower homologue. The reaction was slow and took 4 days for completion; 30g. of the ketone gave only 7.5 g. of the hydroxymethylene ketone. The latter is a light yellow mobile liquid which boils at 124°-125°/50 mm. It gives a reddish violet colour with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 69.6; H, 10.9. $C_{10}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 69.6; H, 10.6 per cent).

Reduction of Hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone: Formation of 2-Methylenecyclohexanone.—Hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone (19 g., b.p. 110°/45 mm.) was mixed with ice-cold water (20 c.c.) in a basin and the mixture made slightly acid with dilute sulphuric acid. Sodium amalgam (prepared from 3.5 g. of sodium) was gradually added with constant rubbing. The mixture was kept at 0° throughout the process and maintained slightly acid. The reaction product was extracted with ether and the ether extract was shaken with dilute caustic soda which dissolved the unchanged hydroxymethylene ketone. The latter was recovered from the alkaline solution on acidifying and was used again in the process of reduction. The neutral ether layer after washing, drying and removal of the solvent left a thick, neutral, viscous mass which gave no colour with ferric chloride, yield 7.5 g. From the viscous liquid a semicarbazone was obtained which after crystallisation from alcohol melted at 228°. (Found: N, 23.9. $C_8H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires N, 23.0 per cent).

The neutral viscous liquid (6 g.) was distilled when practically the whole of it passed steadily at 133°-135°/55 mm. as a thin, mobile, neutral liquid, yield 4 g. The pure liquid (methylenecyclohexanone) was analysed. (Found: C, 75.4; H, 8.7. $C_7H_{10}O$ requires C, 76.3; H, 9.1 per cent).

2-Methylenecyclohexanone is an almost colorless liquid, insoluble in alkali. Its solution in carbon tetrachloride readily absorbs bromine. It forms a semicarbazone which after crystallisation from water melts at 162°. (Found: C, 57.1; H, 7.7. $C_8H_{13}ON_3$ requires C, 57.5; H, 7.8 per cent).

Action of Phosphorus Pentachloride on Hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone: Formation of Dichloroaldehyde (XVI).—Phosphorus pentachloride (15 g.) was added in small instalments to a solution of hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone (8 g.) in dry benzene (25 c.c.) kept in a flask surrounded by ice water and fitted with reflux arrangement. After the addition was over

the flask was heated on a warm water-bath for 15 minutes and the solution was shaken with ice-cold dilute caustic soda which removed the phosphorus halide and also the unchanged hydroxymethylene ketone. The benzene layer was washed with water, dried and the solvent removed when a dark coloured liquid was left which distilled at 126° - $128^{\circ}/50$ mm., yield 7 g. This was analysed. (Found : C, 46.2 ; H, 4.5 ; Cl, 40.2. $C_7H_{10}OCl_2$ requires C, 46.4 ; H, 5.5 ; Cl, 39.5 per cent).

The dichloro aldehyde is a colorless liquid heavier than water. It does not dissolve in alkali and gives no colour with ferric chloride. It readily reduces Fehling's solution and ammoniacal silver nitrate. It is unstable and slowly polymerises to a dark green resinous mass. It forms a semicarbazone which crystallises from acetic acid and melts at 232° . (Found : Cl, 17.6. $C_9H_{12}ON_3Cl$ requires Cl, 17.6. $C_8H_{13}ON_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 29.8 per cent).

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
AGRA COLLEGE, AGRA.

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